

Viscosity of Dilute Solutions of Non-electrolytes.

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A good deal of work has been done on the viscosity of solutions of non-electrolytes, but few workers have used solutions below tenth molal. Various formulæ connecting viscosity and concentration have been proposed (Dunstan and Thole, "Viscosity of Liquids," page 43), but all these relate to moderately concentrated solutions, where the laws of dilute solutions are not applicable.

In the Landolt-Börnstein's tables, viscosities (η) of 1 and 5 % sucrose solutions are given for a number of temperatures. By applying the laws of dilute solution, the vapour pressure (p) of any solution is calculated at the temperature at which the viscosity is measured. It is found that the following relationships hold between the viscosity and vapour pressure of the solutions concerned:—

$$\log \eta = -0.335 \log p - 1.52 \text{ for the 1 \% solution} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$\log \eta = -0.358 \log p - 1.49 \text{ for the 5 \% solution} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

It is quite well known (Porter, *Phil. Mag.*, 1912, 23, 458) that viscosity (η_0) and vapour pressure (p_0) of water are connected together by the equation,

$$\log \eta_0 = -0.362 \log p_0 - 1.54 \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

All the three equations are straight line equations and can be represented by $y = mx + k$, where m and k are different for the different equations. The differences between the m and k values for water and the 5 % solution are large, but then it has to be borne in mind that laws of dilute solution have been applied for calculating the m and k values for the solution which is by no means a dilute one. The difference between the m values of water and the 1 % solution is 0.8 % and that between the k values 1.3 %. Assuming that in still more dilute solutions they would disappear, the two equations (the

one for the solution and the other for the solvent) could be combined to give the equation,

$$\log \eta/\eta_0 = -0.362 \log p/p_0 \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

which after substituting $1-n/N$ (n = number of gram molecules of the solute in N gram molecules of the solvent) for p/p_0 and expanding, assumes the form (the higher power are neglected because of dilution),

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.362 N/n \quad \text{or} \quad \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + aC$$

where $a = 6.52 \times 10^{-3}$ if concentration (C) is measured in gram molecules per litre.

In order to test this equation and consequently the assumption made, viscosity of aqueous solutions of sucrose and fructose were measured at 30°, 35° and 40° and of glucose at 35° and 40° for a number of concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The thermostat used for the experiment was electrically heated and the temperature was controlled by means of a toluene thermo-regulator. The thermostat had a glass window for making observations. It could be lighted when necessary by means of a 25 watt lamp which was kept immersed in the water of the thermostat. The stirring was done electrically. The temperature could be maintained within 0.005°.

Viscosity was measured by means of Ostwald's viscometer. The viscometer was always clamped at the same place. A piece of thread was stretched over the thermostat. After clamping, the viscometer was rotated till the middle part of the wider arm and the edge of the narrower arm, which had a rubber tube attached to it, were in a line with the thread. This procedure ensured that the viscometer was always placed in the same position. Three marks were made; one above the bulb on the capillary side, one below the bulb on the same side and the third above the bulb in the wider limb. The viscometer was so constructed that after the liquid flowed back, it rested in the capillary tube two and half inches below the lower mark on the capillary limb. The liquid in the wider limb was made up to the mark above the bulb in the limb, the liquid in the other limb resting in the capillary tube itself. This ensured that the volume of the liquid taken was the same in every case.

Three to five readings for time were taken in case of every solution. They seldom differed from one another by more than 0.2 seconds. The mean of the time was used in calculating viscosity. Every time, the time of flow for a solution was measured, the same for the water used, was also measured. In case of every solution the weight of the solution, contained in a specific gravity bottle at the temperature concerned, was found to the third place of decimal. η/η_0 was calculated by the formula; $\eta/\eta_0 = tw/t_0w_0$ where t and w denote the time of flow and the weight of the said volume of the solution respectively and t_0 and w_0 the same for pure water. No kinetic correction was considered necessary as (i) the time of flow was quite large, (ii) the bore of the capillary tube was 0.36 mm. only and (iii) time taken by water and solutions did not differ much from each other on account of the solutions being dilute.

In the following tables, C , η/η_0 and α are given for the various solutions.

TABLE I.

Sucrose solutions.

$C \times 10^3$.	30°		35°		40°	
	η/η_0 .	α .	η/η_0 .	α .	η/η_0 .	α .
2.339	1.0017	0.727	1.0016	0.684	1.0022	0.941
4.678	1.0034	0.727	1.0037	0.791	1.0039	0.834
7.018	1.0053	0.755	1.0056	0.798	1.0053	0.755
9.357	1.0072	0.769	1.0077	0.823	1.0077	0.823
11.696	1.0086	0.735	1.0089	0.761	1.0092	0.787
14.035	1.0101	0.720	1.0111	0.790	1.0116	0.827
16.374	1.0131	0.800	1.0129	0.788	1.0127	0.776
18.714	1.0159	0.849	1.0141	0.748	1.0145	0.775
21.053	1.0178	0.846	1.0177	0.841	1.0168	0.798
	α Mean = 0.780		α Mean = 0.770		Mean value of α for the last eight figures = 0.797	

TABLE II.

Fructose solutions.

30°			35°			40°		
$C \times 10^3$.	η/η_0 .	α .	$C \times 10^3$.	η/η_0 .	α .	$C \times 10^3$.	η/η_0 .	α .
2.484	1.0011	0.443	2.293	1.0008	0.350	2.947	1.0012	0.407
4.627	1.0022	0.475	3.964	1.0020	0.505	5.067	1.0022	0.434
7.409	1.0031	0.418	6.729	1.0025	0.372	7.000	1.0033	0.471
9.058	1.0038	0.419	8.462	1.0038	0.449	10.142	1.0037	0.365
12.562	1.0054	0.430	11.831	1.0049	0.414	12.397	1.0047	0.379
15.344	1.0066	0.430	15.324	1.0064	0.418	14.684	1.0082	0.422
17.800	1.0077	0.433	16.444	1.0071	0.432	16.418	1.0071	0.432
20.238	1.0090	0.445	19.196	1.0078	0.406	19.556	1.0077	0.394
22.724	1.0097	0.427	20.755	1.0082	0.395	21.444	1.0084	0.392
26.756	1.0112	0.419	22.804	1.0090	0.395	25.667	1.0099	0.386
Mean value of $\alpha = 0.434$			Mean value of $\alpha = 0.414$			Mean value of $\alpha = 0.408$		

TABLE III.

Glucose solutions.

35°			40°		
$C \times 10^3$.	η/η_0 .	α .	$C \times 10^3$.	η/η_0 .	α .
2.969	1.0016	0.539	2.127	1.0013	0.611
4.348	1.0022	0.507	4.000	1.0022	0.550
6.240	1.0027	0.433	7.111	1.0032	0.450
9.347	1.0039	0.417	9.160	1.0039	0.426
10.484	1.0043	0.410	11.480	1.0052	0.453
13.751	1.0060	0.436	13.658	1.0060	0.439
15.315	1.0070	0.451	15.853	1.0068	0.429
18.387	1.0073	0.397	18.124	1.0074	0.408
20.849	1.0085	0.408	20.271	1.0085	0.419
25.715	1.0106	0.412	24.453	1.0104	0.425
Mean value of $\alpha = 0.441$			Mean value of α for the last nine figures only = 0.444.		

In the following figure η/η_0 is plotted against concentration for the solution of each of the solutes at 40°. The values for other temperatures also behave in the same way.

It is evident from the tables as well as the diagram that a is fairly constant for any solute. Its variation with temperature is within experimental error. Even if it varies with temperature, the variation is not very marked. However it is not independent of solute thus conclusively proving that the assumption made in deducing equation (iv) is wrong.

SUMMARY.

1. The viscosity of dilute solutions of sucrose and fructose has been measured at 30°, 35° and 40° and of glucose at 35° and 40°.
2. All these viscosities can be represented by the equation $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + aC$ where a is independent of temperature, but not of the solute.
3. The value of a for sucrose solutions is about 0.78, fructose 0.42 and glucose 0.44.
4. The concentration range is 2×10^{-3} to 27×10^{-3} g. molecules per litre.

